

The Grief and Loneliness in Rabindranath Tagore's The Holidays

Harini. V

II M.A English Literature, Dr. GR Damodaran College of Science, Coimbatore

Yasmin Fathima. M

II M.A English Literature, Dr. GR Damodaran College of Science, Coimbatore

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15533342>

Abstract

Indian English literature began as interesting by-products of an eventful encounter in the late 18th century between a vigorous and enterprising Britain and a stagnant and chaotic India. This paper explores the complex dynamics of human relationships through the lens of a family gathering. The story delves into the contrasting personalities of the characters and their struggles with adapting to the changing social landscape. The Holidays shows the difference between simple village life and the harshness of city life, the emotional effects of being separated from loved ones and the often-overlooked sacrifices mothers make. Through Phatik's difficult journey, Tagore criticizes the pressure society puts on children and shows how important a mother's love is. The paper also explores how Tagore's storytelling, which is realistic and emotionally powerful, makes The Holiday a story that speaks to us about childhood struggles and human relationships even today. By examining the story's themes and writing techniques, this paper aims to show how The Holiday is still relevant when we talk about education, parenting, and the emotional needs of children.

Keywords: *Care, Protection, Emotional Distance, Sacrificial Love*

The emotional distancing in the story is shown through the lack of warmth and affection between the characters. Phatik's mother does not openly show her love when he is alive, and his uncle's family does not make him feel at home. This emotional distance leads to Phatik's deep sadness and eventual tragedy, highlighting how a lack of emotional connection can have heartbreaking consequences. Phatik, feeling lonely and unwanted, longs to return home. His longing deepens when he falls sick, and in his feverish state, he repeatedly asks if he can go back. Tragically, he dies before he can reunite with his mother. At the end of the story, his mother arrives too late, overwhelmed with sorrow, realizing too late how much she loved and missed him. The story revolves around Phatik, a young boy who is sent away from his village home to live with his uncle in the city. His mother, though she loves him, struggles to express her emotions openly. Similarly, his uncle's family does not welcome him warmly, treating him as a burden.

Rabindranath Tagore's short story The Holidays (Chhuti) is a poignant narrative that explores themes of grief, loneliness, and the deep longing for love and connection. The story revolves around Phatik Chakravarti, a restless and mischievous young boy who is sent away from his village home to live with his uncle in Kolkata. Through Phatik's journey, Tagore delves into the emotional turmoil of a child torn away from familiarity, reflecting on the universal human experience of loss and isolation.

Phatik is introduced as an energetic and playful boy living in a rural village with his widowed mother and younger brother. His life, though filled with mischief, is marked by a sense of belonging and freedom. However, he often feels misunderstood, especially by his mother, who appears to favor his younger brother. His desire for adventure and recognition leads him into trouble, and his mother struggles to manage his rebellious spirit.

Phatik's life takes a turn when his maternal uncle visits from Kolkata and offers to take him to the city for better education. His mother, frustrated and overwhelmed, agrees, despite Phatik's initial reluctance. However, he soon grows excited about the journey, unaware of the profound loneliness that awaits him. Upon reaching Kolkata, Phatik realizes that his new life is far from what he had imagined. His uncle is cold and indifferent, while his aunt finds him to be an unnecessary burden. Unlike his village, where he had the company of friends and open fields to play in, the city feels confining and alien. The academic pressure, the lack of affection, and the constant scolding make him feel unwanted.

This isolation deepens his grief, as he yearns for his mother's love and the familiar comfort of home. However, in a tragic irony, he was sent away because his mother seemed indifferent to him, and now, he longs for the very presence he once resented. The emotional distance between Phatik and his family in Kolkata mirrors the physical distance from his home, reinforcing the theme of alienation.

Phatik's loneliness soon takes a toll on his health. He falls ill, and in his feverish state, he repeatedly asks if he can go home. His uncle, realizing the depth of the boy's suffering too late, finally sends for his mother. By the time she arrives, Phatik is on the verge of death. His last words expressing his longing to return home encapsulate the tragedy of his unfulfilled desire for love and belonging. This is the age when boys experience psychological and physical changes. They tend to grow very fast. In such a situation, Home and Mother are unbearable to the boys. This was the case of Phatik Chakrabarti too. When his Uncle offered to take him to Kolkata, Phatik readily agreed to go. But, once in Kolkata, he found himself in a loveless environment. He longs for those days in his village. He wanted to go back to his Mother, but he can only go during the Pooja Holidays. Phatik and his friends were playing, and suddenly they got an idea to roll a log into the river. Phatik's younger brother Makhanlal came and solemnly sat on the log. One of the boys tried to push him off, but he refused to budge.

He is not ready to come up, the boys stress in his haughty, dismissive attitude. Phatik said "You'll pay for this" (Holiday, p.2). Makhanlal merely adjusted his perch and settled down even more immovably on the log. Phatik got tense and slapped his cheeks but he didn't dare. Phatik rolled the log over with Makhanlal on it. The boys rolled up their sleeves and began to push "Heave ho! Heave ho! Over We Go!" (p.3). With one spin Makhan's solemnity, glory and wisdom crashed to the ground.

Makhan immediately jumped up and threw himself on to him, with blind rage and scratching his nose and cheeks. Then he made his way home tearfully. The game having been spoiled, Pathik collected some reeds, and climbed on the half-sunk boat and sat quietly chewing them. A boat, not a local one, came up to the mooring-place. A middle-aged gentleman with a black moustache and grey hair stepped. He asked where Phatik Chakravarti's house was. Phatik replied over there, still chewing the reed-stalks. The man did not understand which direction to take. He again asked where, Pathik said he did not know and he started to chew the reeds as before. Now the gentleman needs to ask for help from others. Suddenly Bagha Bagdi appeared and said, Phatik Mother was calling him. Phatik said he cannot go. Bagha picked him up and carried him home. His mother shouted furiously when she saw him,

'You've beaten Makhan again!'

'I didn't beat him up.'

'How dare you lie to me?'

'I did not beat him up. Ask him.'

When Makhan was questioned, he stuck to his earlier accusation, saying 'He did beat me up.' (p.4) So who is lying now, asked mother. His mother, taking Makhan's part, rushed Pathik's back several times heavily. He pushed her away. Phatik laid his hands over his mother, she screamed.

The narrative of the story is to present us with one side of the children's character while keeping the other absent, and then coming up with the other weaker part of their beings, contradicting the previous versions of what was presented, but hardly able to defeat the first impression. The initial

impressions are more powerful and therefore stick to the mind a little more solidly than what follows. The traces are there, as if apparently absent but always already present in the character of the brothers.

There is a similarity between the brothers which is cleverly kept hidden by Tagore, again as an absence in the narrative. Both of them are no saints; they are mischievous. Each wants to give some kind of displeasure to the other and finds some kind of fun in the other's annoyance. Even as they appear to be dissimilar, the brothers are quite similar. Though the text is silent on the issue of genetic transmission of human traits, a slower reading and understanding of the text could suggest that the two brothers are ultimately like their mother; she shares with her sons in not being quite fair in what she does. She has not been just to Phatik. She alleges that Phatik is a liar, when Makhan complains against him, without trying to investigate the matter at all.

Tagore was anxious about not writing too much like Rudyard Kipling when he wrote *Holiday*. Tagore's writing of other narrative texts like *Holiday* could have the ghosts of some of Kipling's other writings. Kipling's *Jungle Book* (1894) is the story of a child brought up by animals in the purer, de-socialized world of the forest. Tagore's *Holiday* could be seen as a reversal of Kipling, as a story about a boy sent from a village or natural setting to the urban town of Calcutta where he cannot thrive in the socially advanced but unnatural situation.

The deconstruction reveals certain contradictions in the text, along with certain absences, it is possible to go beyond and see how Tagore was writing a frame of mind that made him write the story with a particular colonial master in the background. Thus, giving birth to a child-hero like Phatik who, like Kipling's *Mowgli*, would develop more healthily in his rural and natural setting. He has been trying to implement the laws of the jungle, using brute force to get what he desires and collapsing when he is forced into the urban world and the schooling of Calcutta. In this, Phatik is portrayed almost like an animal that would not be able to take the burden of living in a big city.

Tagore had thought independently, as one who loved the villages of Bengal as much as he did the urban settings, that it is quite natural to present Phatik almost as a symbol of nature. He was one of the few Indians of his time who understood the soul of rural India even as he appreciated the richness of western civilization. Phatik could well be Tagore's idea of the soul of rural India that needed to be protected from the encroaching west and urbanization. The boy from the village pines for home; runs away from an inhuman abode.

He starts his homeward journey alone; it is his soul that reaches home. The play is a metaphor of today's urban childhood set against its tragic loss. Poetically, the play is a search to know 'what is home and where is home.' Enacted by a group of children under 12, the play is a realistic representation of an ideal dream. The activities here address the innate artist in a child. As grassroots experiences in life, here is something that makes "the Child, the father of the Man." The country life is generally understood to be pure and uncorrupted. The same holds in this story.

Here the readers have come to the end of the Project on the topic of the grief of loneliness with the contrast between the country life and the village life. There is a green lush of 'glorious meadow', river banks and open spaces. A city is deprived of such natural gifts; instead, it is congested with concrete jungles. Phatik was 'ringleader' amongst his friends in the village, while in Calcutta; he is left neglected like a stray dog that has lost its master. The boy whose proposal was unanimously second in the village, finds himself being jeered and insulted by his cousins in Calcutta.

Tagore has made interesting observations on a boy of fourteen. It is indeed true that puberty and teenage are times when we are in a state of confusion, owing to several physical, mental and moral changes in ourselves. Puberty is the intermediate stage between childishness and youth. We fail to identify ourselves with either. That is why we crave a sense of belongingness at this age. Phatik, who longs for love and acceptance in his aunt's home but fails to get it.

Here the readers can compare the story *Holiday* with the poem *I Cannot Remember My Mother* by Rabindranath Tagore. Both the work themes are longing for the mother. In the case of *Holiday*, the character falls on the stage of being an adult, but in the case of *I Cannot Remember My Mother*, the character does not remember his mother, who died in his tender age. Tagore stated in his poem as,

“I cannot remember my mother
Only sometimes in the midst of my play
a tune seems to hover over my playthings,
the tune of some song that she used to hum while rocking
my cradle.” (p.118)

He cannot remember his mother now. However, he feels her presence pervading into his life, when he is in the middle of his play with his playthings, he senses a tune hovering over him. It is the tune of his mother’s song which she used to hum while rocking his cradle. When it is the early autumn morning, the smell of shiuli flowers floats in the air. Then the poet smells the scent of the morning service in the temple. In that smell, he senses the scent of his mother. He looks out into the blue of the distant sky when the poet is in the bedroom. He feels his mother’s silent, steady and protective gaze being cast down at him from her heavenly abode. Her face seems to be spread all over the sky.

A child who has lost his mother at a tender age misses her every moment. He remembers her and feels her presence everywhere, yet he repeats *I cannot remember my mother* probably because he cannot remember how she looked and has just a faint recollection. The poet has used vivid, diverse and powerful imagery to depict the feelings and pain of a child who has lost his mother. The child poet says that he can feel the presence of his mother as, sometimes, the tune of that song that she used to hum while rocking his cradle, seems to hover over his playthings. The fragrance of shiuli flowers and the scent of the morning prayer service, appears to be the fragrance of his mother.

The poem is both emotional and moving. The poet feels the presence of his mother all round him, though he has only a faint recollection of her real self. The different occasions on which he is haunted by her memory show his longing to be loved and cared for by his mother. Even though his mother is not alive, she has a significant role in his life. He knows his mother is always with him. From this bedroom window he looks at the blue of the distant sky, he feels the gaze of his mother, showering all her blessings, lovingly. This comforts him and makes him feel protected. It is full of cultural, religious or humanistic relationships with the things described.

The story *Holiday* brings out the sad fate of Pathik Charabarti who fails to chip in through the city life. The last line of the story “Mother, the holidays have come” (*Holiday*, p.13) continues to haunt the readers, what exactly happened with Phatik. The binary opposite plays here, whether Phatik expired. There is a strong possibility that Pathik entered the long sleep of eternity. However, we are not told what happens next. It is left for the readers to surmise as per their understanding and it is this ambiguity that makes this story so interesting.

One thing that can be safely concluded is that Pathik’s *Holiday* for going home is not the village home that he longed for, but some other home. It is left for the readers to decipher the softer meanings of that some other home where we are will enter, someday or the other. The boy had been given to understand that he could go back to his village and to his mother only during the holidays; his mother’s presence brings him great joy and peace and, so, for him the holidays have begun. Then, holidays also signify freedom and liberty, and home signifies the eternal home. The problem with boys of their age period (12-14 years old) is that they are in between, no longer children but not yet adults. Thus they are no longer given the accommodating tolerance that little kids get. The short story *Holiday* may indicate a part of Tagore’s life, because his Mother Sarada Devi died in 1875 when he was at the age of eighteen.

Work Cited

1. Tagore, Rabindranath. Holiday. Oxford University Press, 2017.
2. Tagore, Rabindranath. I Cannot Remember My Mother. (e book)
3. Kipling, Rudyard. Jungle Book.(e book)